

Digitalization and MSME Financial Performance: the Time of the COVID-19 Pandemic

^{1*)} Dwi Saraswati, ²⁾ Ardhansyah Putra Harahap

^{1,2.)} Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

Abstract: This study aims to assist practitioners in identifying strategies needed to respond to the impact of the ongoing pandemic on MSMEs and assist companies in predicting risks in the early stages of business decision-making and planning, and determine the action to be taken. The method used is qualitative descriptive. The population in this study is MSMEs in Medan city. The sampling technique was simple random sampling. Data collection was by questionnaire and sample collection period 2 months with a total sample of 37 questionnaires obtained. The results of this study are that many MSMEs have been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, 43% of MSMEs have capital constraints, the impact of COVID-19 on MSMEs is that only 50% of the results survive. COVID-19 pandemic data and some others have stopped temporarily due to lack of capital and PPKM government policies. Strategies that are done by MSMEs to be able to operate during a pandemic by adding capital by 47% and using information technology by 29%. The use of information technology is carried out as a promotional media in the form of: WhatsApp at 88%, Facebook and Instagram at 6% each. Impact of COVID-19 also affects the financial performance of 75% of MSMEs, 75% earn a turnover of less than Rp. 30,000,000.00 and 25% of MSMEs have sales turnover Rp. 30,000,000-Rp. 50,000,000.

Keywords: Financial performance, MSMEs, COVID-19.

I. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic is a disaster that has swept across the country and has an impact on health and the economy. From an economic point of view, all companies in the world experienced a significant impact from the COVID-19 outbreak on their business. In particular, companies are facing various problems such as declining demand, supply chain problems, cancellation of export orders, shortage of raw materials, and transportation. The crisis that occurs when the COVID-19 pandemic is bigger than the 1998 crisis because it happened in various places, ranging from security, trade, to labor and poverty levels. Restrictions on community activities reduce people's purchasing and consumptive power. The main victims of the COVID-19 outbreak are micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) compared to large companies because MSMEs do not have sufficient resources, especially financial and managerial, and are unprepared for the devastating COVID-19 pandemic, which will likely last longer than expected (Bartik et al., 2020; Alex, 2020; Prasad et al., 2015). MSMEs must innovate both in terms of products and services marketing. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the domestic economy in Indonesia, namely a decrease in people's consumption and purchasing power, a decline in company performance, threats to the banking and financial sector, as well as the existence of MSMEs (Ministry of Finance). MSMEs are the backbone of many economies around the world which provide income and job creation for many people around the world. Likewise in Indonesia, MSMEs provide a significant GDP, namely reaching 61.97% of the total national GDP in 2020 or Rp. 8,500 trillion. MSMEs are able to absorb a lot of people, amounting to 97% percent of the absorption capacity of the business world in 2020.

MSMEs need to adapt to situations where the COVID-19 pandemic threatens their businesses. One way to keep businesses afloat in this situation is to use technology. Based on a survey conducted by the Asia Pacific Foundation Canada about Entrepreneurs and MSMEs in Indonesia, Information Communication and Technology Adoption (ICT) is still a challenge for small businesses due to lack of capabilities and resources to adapt to significant technological improvements. But not a little MSMEs that have risen and recovered in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. MSMEs that are recovering are those who can adapt to pandemic conditions, then make designs and implement new strategies in doing business through E-Commerce as a means of marketplace.

supported by digital marketing. Another challenge that must be faced by MSMEs in Indonesia is the development of technology that is developing so rapidly. MSMEs must adapt to technology to more reach the market. With the consumption pattern of people who prefer shopping online forces MSMEs to innovate with online shopping methods on line. The importance of digital transformation for MSMEs cannot be overstated. Not only as a platform for sales, but also for corporate activities such as marketing, customer outreach, product information, customer retention, and customer service. Research conducted by Hadion (2020) states that Networking, engaging with customers, and introduce the company's products or services all need a good digital marketing plan.

The internet and the ability to use these digital devices are important and must be mastered by MSMEs if they want to compete (Purwana, Rahmi, & Aditya, 2017). In research conducted by Deloitte Access Economics (2015) it is stated that Consumers in today's era are getting used to making decisions based on content digital and make online purchases. This is a challenge but also is a promising business opportunity for MSMEs in Indonesia. This study aims to assist practitioners in identifying strategies that needed to respond to the impact of the ongoing pandemic on MSMEs and assist companies in predicting risk at an early stage of taking decisions and business planning, and determine the actions to be taken. Based on this, a plan for digitizing MSMEs was drawn up to support development and as input for MSME actors in implementing digitalization in its business operations after COVID-19.

II. Methodology

The research method used in this research is descriptive method qualitative. The population in this study are SMEs in Medan. Technique sampling with simple random sampling and the period of this research lasts for 2 months, namely October-November 2021. Within 2 months In this study, 37 questionnaires were filled out completely.

The data collection technique in this study used interview and interview techniques questionnaire. Interviews were conducted directly with SMEs in Indonesia Medan city. Questionnaires were distributed to Medan City SMEs offline because at that time Indonesia had experienced a decline in the covid-19 outbreak and to make it easier respondents to fill out the questionnaire. Before the questionnaire was distributed to respondents, the items the questionnaire was pilottested among a small sample of business owners to evaluate clarity and the relevance of the questionnaire items to identify and eliminate potential problems.

The questionnaire consists of 10 question items. Questionnaire items include several questions about basic information about the company and its characteristics (such as size and industry), impact of the COVID-19 Outbreak on business, decline in sales and profit, period the survival of SMEs, the period of business normalization.

Figure 1. Distribution of MSME Actors Based on Sector

III. Results

Problems and obstacles faced by MSMEs due to COVID-19

The obstacles faced by MSMEs during the COVID-19 pandemic are presented in Figure 1. Constraints faced by MSME actors as much as 43% in the form of limited business capital, there are obstacles due to the increase in raw material prices by 28%. Apart from that, the problem of going down 24.30% buyers, 3% of raw material availability constraints due to enforcement limitation of activities and constraints of sick employees 2%

Figure 2. Constraints Faced by MSMEs in Medan During the Pandemic

The COVID-19 outbreak has had a significant impact on MSME turnover in Medan, based on the results of the questionnaire the results were 94.62% experienced a decrease in turnover (Figure 3). With a long pandemic and it is not known when it will end, then SMEs are worried that the survival period of their business will not be long because limited capital. This is in line with Senz's (2020) research on the impact of COVID 19 on MSME operations in America, the results show that 65% of small businesses believe that they cannot survive the ongoing crisis lasts four months. Covid-19 also has an impact on business operations, MSMEs continue to operate as much as 50%, some MSMEs tried to stop because there was no demand as much as 23%, MSMEs had stopped because 17% of capital and 10% had stopped temporarily because of PPKM. The results of this study are in line with a survey conducted by the National Small Business Association, the results show 49% of those surveyed small businesses experience decreased customer demand, and 33% experienced supply chain disruptions, while 20% experienced employee absenteeism (NSBA, 2020). This result is not surprising because of gravity of the ongoing problems even worse than the financial crisis of the

Figure 3. Impact of Business Operations During the COVID-19 Pandemic for MSMEs in Medan

Strategies for SMEs to deal with COVID-19

Many consumption behaviors have changed during the COVID-19 pandemic, and these changes are driven by government regulations. As is the case with government restrictions on the implementation of social restrictions, when all community activities are restricted and advised to stay at home. However, this is very difficult for society, given the continuing human needs, and the fact that they are restricted in their movement to stay at home. The

COVID-19 pandemic has changed the behavior of consumers who initially looked for needs directly by visiting the place, now changing by looking for needs online.

The strategy to survive during the pandemic is by way of MSME owners adding 47% of capital and using information technology by 29% (figure 4). The existence of technology is very helpful during social restrictions because consumers are freer and easier to transact so they don't have to leave the house. For SMEs, it is also very efficient because they do not need brochures and can update their products at any time through social media. This research is in line with Hardilawati (2019) which results in information technology having a positive impact on the development of MSMEs.

Figure 4. Strategies Performed by MSMEs in Medan During the Pandemic

In the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic crisis, there are still many MSMEs that survive with various strategies that are carried out, especially in the marketing process (digital marketing). In Century the current Covid-19 pandemic, MSME actors must be technology literate so that their business does not experiencing a downturn, MSME actors in Sukoharjo take advantage of promotional media with WhatsApp details as much as 88% Facebook and Instagram are each used as much as 6% (figure 5). Speed in adapting to increasingly technology sophisticated technology makes MSME actors not out of date. Research results Asbari et al (2021) revealed that the use of social media in digital marketing has an impact on increase in start-up business revenue. However, in reality, some MSME actors don't use digital means, admits that they can't use the internet with correct.

Figure 5. Promotional Media used by SMEs in Medan

The Covid-19 pandemic has an impact on the level of sales turnover during the pandemic. Fairlie's (2020) research with the method of distributing surveys and the results show During the Covid-19 pandemic, MSMEs faced a drastic decline in sales, which also lead to liquidity problems. In Figure 6 it can be seen that the sales turnover of

SMEs In Medan during the Covid-19 pandemic, 75% of MSMEs received a turnover less than Rp. 30,000,000.00 and 25% of MSMEs have a sales turnover of Rp. 30,000,000 - Rp. 50,000,000. Results of an interview with Mr. Gunawan as a food trader in Medan stated: "The sales turnover before the Covid-19 pandemic could reach above Rp. 30,000,000 due to the government's policy to reduce activities outside the home for consumers so that the merchandise does not sell and there are a lot of leftovers. This is in line with the Covid-19 impact on sales and revenue MSMEs, according to a survey conducted by the LIPI Economic Research Center. More than 70% MSME experienced a decline in sales and profitability of more than 50%. Costs on the other hand experience such as raw material costs, transportation costs, and labor costs.

Figure 6. MSME Sales Turnover in Medan During the Pandemic

IV. Conclusion

The Indonesian economy is highly dependent on MSMEs. According to Ministry data Cooperatives and SMEs there are

64.2 million MSMEs in Indonesia, contributing 61.07 percent of GDP or Rp. 8,573.89 trillion. This research was conducted to assess the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on MSMEs in Medan in order to ease the burden of the crisis experienced SMEs today. The results of this study found that the COVID-19 outbreak caused many MSMEs to be affected 43% of MSMEs have capital constraints, because they do not have capital enough to deal with the storm of the Covid-19 pandemic. In addition, the impact on MSMEs As respondents in this study, only 50% survived the Covid-19 pandemic data and others have temporarily stopped due to lack of capital and policies government in social restrictions.

Strategies carried out by MSMEs to be able to operate during a pandemic by adding capital by 47% and using information technology by 29%. The use of information technology is carried out as a promotional media so that products from SMEs stay afloat during the pandemic, the type of promotional media from WhatsApp is 88%, Facebook and Instagram 6% each. The impact of covid-19 also affects financial performance MSMEs as much as 75% MSMEs get a turnover of less than Rp. 30,000,000.00 and 25% MSMEs have a sales turnover of Rp. 30,000,000-Rp. 50,000,000.

References

- [1.] Asbari, M., Dylmoon Hidayat, D., & Purwanto, A. (2021). Managing Employee Performance: From Leadership to Readiness for Change. *International Journal of Social and Management Studies*, 2(1), 74-85.
- [2.] Bartik, A., Bertrand, M., Cullen, Z. B., Glaeser, E. L., Luca, M., & Stanton, C. (2020). How are small businesses adjusting to COVID-19? Early evidence from a survey. *Harvard Business School Working Paper*, 20(102), 1-37.
- [3.] Delloitte Access Economics. 2015. *UKM Pemicu Kemajuan Indonesia Instrumen Pertumbuhan Nusantara*.
- [4.] Fairlie, R. W. (2020). The Impact of Covid-19 on Small Business Owners: Evidence of Early Stage Losses From the April 2020 Current Population Survey. *NBER Working Paper Series*, (June). Retrieved from <http://www.nber.org/papers/w27309>
- [5.] Hardilawati WL, "Strategi Bertahan UMKM Di tengah Pandemi Covid-19", *jurnal akuntansi dan ekonomika*, Vol 10. No.1, Juni 2020, hal 94.

- [6.] Hartono dan Deny Dwi Hartono. 2014. Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Perkembangan UMKM di Surakarta, (*Jurnal Bisnis & Manajemen*, Vol. 14, No. 1, 2014: 15-30).
- [7.] NSBA. 2020. Small business impact poll. National Small Business Association of U.S.
- [8.] Purwana, D., Rahmi, & Aditya, S. 2017. Pemanfaatan Digital Marketing Bagi Usaha Mikro, Kecil, Dan Menengah (UMKM) Di Kelurahan Malaka Sari, Duren Sawit. *Jurnal Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Madani (JPPM)* 1(1): 1 -17.
- [9.] Prasad, S., Su, H. -C., Altay, N., & Tata, J. (2015). Building disaster-resilient micro enterprises in the developing world. *Disasters*, 39(3), 447-466.
- [10.] Salam, Muhammad Aminul Khoiri. 2020. Perilaku Produksi di Tengah Krisis Global Akibat Pandemi Covid-19 dan Memanfaatkan Media Online Facebook Sebagai Alternatif Pasar, (*Jurnal Ekonomi, Manajemen dan Akuntansi*).
- [11.] Sarmigi, Alex. 2020. Analisis pengaruh covid terhadap perkembangan UMKM dkabupaten kerinci. *Jurnal Al-Dzahab* Vol. 1 (1) 2020.
- [12.] Senz, K. (2020). Small businesses are worse off than we thought. Harvard Business School Working Knowledge. [13.] Slamet, R., Nainggolan, B., Roessobiyatno, Ramdani, H., Hendriyanto, A., & Lu'ul, I. L. 2016. Strategi Pengembangan UKM Digital Dalam Menghadapi Era Pasar Bebas. *Jurnalmanajemen Indonesia* 16(2): 136 -147
- [14.] Wijoyo, Hadion dan Widianti. 2020. Digitalisasi UMKM pasca pandemi covid-19 di riau. *Prosiding Sinagara*, Hal. 12, Desember 2020.